

Microsoft Excel Skills as Antidotes Towards Achievement of Economic Development among Secretarial Administration Students

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ABSTRACT: The study examined Microsoft excel skills as antidotes towards achievement of economic development among secretarial administration students. Two research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design. Was used. The population of this study comprised all postgraduate business education students in Olabisi Onabanjo University and Tai Solarin University of Education, Ogun State. A total of 100 postgraduate business education students in Olabisi Onabanjo University and Tai Solarin University of Education, Ogun State served as sample size of the study. Stratified sampling technique was used in the process of selecting the sample size with the view to ensure gender balance. Researcher developed instrument tagged: Microsoft Excel Skills and Economic Development Questionnaire (MESEDQ) with 0.87 as reliability coefficient was used for data collection. Research questions 1 and 2 were analyses using mean and standard deviation as well as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The findings of the study revealed that manipulate skill, manipulating symbols, to print document skill, reprographic machines skills, change paper layout skill, save information skills, delete information skill, copy/paste information skill, merge two or more documents, assign files name, bold numbers skill and underscore words skill were among Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development by secretarial administration students. There was relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development ($r = 5.16, p < .05$). The secretarial administration curriculum should seek to produce graduates that are critical and creative thinkers, with real skills, those who are ready to challenge the status quo, ready to make mistakes and learn from them. Graduates who are not afraid to put forward novel ideas, listen to others and be ready to compromise where necessary.

KEYWORDS: Microsoft excel skills, Economic Development, Secretarial Administration Student

INTRODUCTION

Every countries of the world are seeking for ways to achieve economic development, particularly among graduates of universities. A situation whereby graduates after finishing from the universities and find no job to do are worrisome and of major concern to the collective authority. The parents are raising eye-brown seeing their children after spending huge sum of resources on their education and at the end they could not secure employment after graduation. Graduates economic development could be seen as one of the ways for achieving economic prosperity in the economy. Economic Development is programs, policies or activities that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community. Economic development ties closely to growth. It centers around how the economy advances to subsequently become wealthier and benefit citizens. Economic development refers to how an economy advance. Its importance lies in how it enables producers and consumers to operate more efficiently and live wealthier. The sole aim of economic development is to reduces unemployment for prosperity. Okon (2024) stated that economic development is a process that influences growth and restructuring of an economy to enhance the economic well-being of a community. The huge amounts of money the government has been investing on the process of attaining economic development over the years have not yielded meaningful result in Nigeria with the current level of poverty in the country.

It has been realized in recent years that there are limits to which government can singly promote economic development. Most of the traditional functions being carried out by the government in most countries ranging from the provision of economic development are becoming increasingly difficult to accomplish. Nigeria as a nation has her own peculiar developmental challenges because of mal-administration, corruption, infrastructural decay, insecurity of lives and properties, unstable macroeconomic policies and unpredictable fiscal policies by successive administrations (Adeyemi & Olabosinde, 2022). Thus, both the public and the private sectors of the economy and every segment of the society need to be involved in the economic development process of the country. However, successive administrations in Nigeria introduced formal education which enabled people to have the opportunity to be employed in the civil service after graduation. As such, the system destroyed the self-reliance, self-employment, and entrepreneurial

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skills of Nigerians as they became permanently dependent on their colonial masters this led to massive unemployment and Craze in the contemporary times of ready-made jobs. Making graduates self-employed towards the achievement of economic development according to Azih (2016) required such graduates to have acquired skills such as Microsoft-excel skills to operate self-business.

Azih (2016) described Microsoft excels as one of the most versatile and popular spreadsheet programs. It serves as an electronic pad for accountants. It can easily perform simple as well as complex mathematical operations. Excel also provides the facility to convert the spreadsheet data into various charts like bar, pie, 2D, and 3D. When converted into charts, the spreadsheet data can easily be understood. The micro soft access and micro soft excel program will ensure that the graduates of the programme develop relevant and saleable competencies that would enable the recipients to be self-employed and also create employment after graduation. Microsoft access which is a subset of Microsoft office applications is a form of database management system (DBMS) designed by Microsoft Corporation to facilitate data independence, shareability, consistency and non-redundancy. Microsoft Access is a database management system software that controls the structure of database and access to data. It is the application that enables an organisation to centralise data, manage them efficiently, and provide access to the stored data by application programmes (Tony-Okeme, 2021). It has the ability to quickly search extremely large numbers of records and fields for commonalities and then help the user generate detailed and complete report for decision making. Microsoft Access application competency is evident in students' ability to create a database, set field properties, modify table structure, create database tables, create a database using wizard, open database tables in datasheet view, change/illustrate table structure, specify data types, enter date and time, switch between design view and datasheet view amongst others (Tony-Okeme, 2021).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There exist diverse economic, social, and political problems at different magnitudes facing nations of the world and the third world countries are not excluded. These diverse economic, social, and political problems have adversely affected the sustainable development of the countries, including the high unemployment rate they are currently facing. Unemployment has become a global phenomenon of the 21st century; the problem is becoming more complex with each passing year in Nigeria. Unemployment, underemployment, and rural-urban migration have enveloped the Nigerian labor market. This has been compounded by a frightening number of graduates from polytechnics, colleges of education, mono-technics, and universities that leave school each year. This has increased the rate of social vices like robbery, kidnapping, prostitution, human trafficking, child abuse, and unfair labor practices experienced in Nigeria. Annually, the problem of this study revolved around the high rate of unemployment, low productivity and slow rate of economic development among universities graduates. The present situation seems to give an impression of economic insecurity as a result of failure to properly engage people in the production process. This study examined Microsoft excel skills as antidotes towards achievement of economic development among secretarial administration students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study was to examine Microsoft excel skills as antidotes towards achievement of economic development among secretarial administration students. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. identify Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development;
2. relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development;

Research Questions

1. What are the Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development?
2. Is there any relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development?

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey research design assisted the researcher to determine the predictive power of explanatory variables on dependent variable. The population of this study comprised all postgraduate business education students in Olabisi Onabanjo University and Tai Solarin University of Education, Ogun State. A total of 100 postgraduate business education students in Olabisi Onabanjo University and Tai Solarin University of Education, Ogun State served as sample size of the study. Stratified sampling technique was used in the process of selecting the sample size with the view to ensure gender balance. Researcher developed instrument tagged: Microsoft Excel Skills and Economic Development Questionnaire (MESEDQ). The questionnaire (MESEDQ) requested responses on a four (4) – point scale format which was a modification of 5-point Likert scale. The questionnaire was divided into 2 sections vis-a-vis sections A and B. Section A focused on demographic characteristics of the respondents while sections B examine items regarding entrepreneurial skills needed for the achievement of economic development; and Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development. Face and content validity of the instrument were done on the instrument. A copy of the instrument was made available to the 3 experts in Business Education to review in content, grammar and structure. Reliability of the instrument was done using the Cronbach alpha. In this case, copies of the instrument were

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administered on 10 business education postgraduate students in Lagos state university. The data that were collected subjected to Cronbach alpha formula to get reliability coefficient of the questionnaire. Reliability coefficient was reported as 0.87. Research questions 1 and 2 were analyses using mean and standard deviation as well as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on the Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development

Items	Mean	SD
Skill to manipulate numbers	2.89	.897
Skills in manipulating symbols.	2.77	.911
Skills to manipulate letters	3.06	.678
Skills to print document	2.99	.900
Ability to manipulate reprographic machines.	2.84	.967
Ability to manipulate text inclined information	2.97	.995
Ability to change paper layout.	2.91	.799
Ability to save information.	2.55	.863
Ability to delete information.	2.90	.843
Ability to copy information	2.73	.894
Ability to merge two or more documents	3.18	.771
Ability to assign files name	3.12	.905
Ability to bold numbers	2.66	.921
Ability to Italicise words	3.01	.763
Ability to underscore words	2.94	.904
Cluster Mean	2.90	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Figure 1: Bar-chart showing Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development

Table 1 indicated that cluster mean was 2.9 which greater than the bench mark of 2.50. $2.9 > 2.5$. This further implied that manipulate skill, manipulating symbols, to print document skill, reprographic machines skills, change paper layout skill, save information skills, delete information skill, copy/paste information skill, merge two or more documents, assign files name, bold numbers skill and underscore words skill were among Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development by secretarial administration students.

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Research Question 2: Is there any relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development?

Table 2: Relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	r _{value}	p _{value}
Microsoft excel skills	100	21.2878	3.10	98	.516	.001
Economic development		17.75	2.60			

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 showed Mean, Standard Deviation and zero order correlation between the variables. It was observed that there was relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable in the order of ($r = 5.16, p < .05$). On this premise, the researcher concluded that there was relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that manipulate skill, manipulating symbols, to print document skill, reprographic machines skills, change paper layout skill, save information skills, delete information skill, copy/paste information skill, merge two or more documents, assign files name, bold numbers skill and underscore words skill were among Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development by secretarial administration students. It was also revealed that there was relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development.

CONCLUSION

Having examined Microsoft excel skills as antidotes towards achievement of economic development among secretarial administration students, the following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study that: manipulate skill, manipulating symbols, to print document skill, reprographic machines skills, change paper layout skill, save information skills, delete information skill, copy/paste information skill, merge two or more documents, assign files name, bold numbers skill and underscore words skill were among Microsoft excel skills needed for the achievement of economic development by secretarial administration students and that there was relationship between Microsoft excel skills and achievement of economic development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are provided:

1. The secretarial administration curriculum should seek to produce graduates that are critical and creative thinkers, with real skills, those who are ready to challenge the status quo, ready to make mistakes and learn from them. Graduates who are not afraid to put forward novel ideas, listen to others and be ready to compromise where necessary.
2. Schools need to improve entrepreneurial insight and the quality of industrial work practices to produce students with good quality vocational high school job readiness.
3. Business Educators should engage students in learning activities that will expose them to practical creative thinking skills needed for a successful entrepreneurship upon graduation, Management Board of Tertiary Institutions should organize seminar/workshops where students will be taught several dimensions of entrepreneurial intentions including Business Alertness by resource persons. This will make graduating Business Education students self-reliant upon graduation.

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